

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to investigate additional private and public funding opportunities that could be applied to the CE solutions addressed in the ECOBULK project to enhance their implementation and deployment at a larger scale and scope.

The first part of this report provides the background information and establishes the funding landscape supporting the circular economy initiatives by looking at relevant European, national and regional schemes (both private and public). The key EU instruments identified and analysed in this report include those active until 2020, such as the Horizon 2020 programme, COSME, InnovFin, the European Fund for Strategic Investments and the Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance (IPA II); as well as permanent or new instruments included in the post-2020 programme such as the Horizon Europe, the European Structural and Investment Funds, LIFE programme, Public contracts, and the European Investment Bank. National and regional funds are also analysed, which are different for each EU country and can be used to support more local projects, as well as to conduct interregional cooperation initiatives under the European programmes. Examples of the national and regional funds are provided for those countries that are present in ECOBULK.

This report also recognises a growing number of private and private-public organisations supporting the circular economy initiatives. The Public-Private Partnerships, such as Sustainable Process Industry (SPIRE), Energy-efficiency Buildings (EeB), The Joint Technology on Bio-based Industries (BBI) and Factories of the Future (FoF), start to be considered as important measures to accelerate the circular economy transition. The private financial instruments include banks, venture capitals, business angels, incubators, foundations, professional associations and corporations.

The first part of this deliverable has been used as a tool for providing key information available to all of those interested in the EU funding programmes, as well as other national and regional programmes (both public and private) supporting the circular economy initiatives.

In the second part of the deliverable, a strategy for seeking additional funding for the ECOBULK consortium is decided. The proposals for further development are identified based on the key exploitation opportunities raised, and the most suitable funding tools selected. Several development pathways are likely to continue beyond ECOBULK in international projects including two or more ECOBULK partners. Horizon Europe is the most promising funding opportunity for supporting further progress in circular economy concepts already analysed in the ECOBULK project.

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1. Introduction

In December 2015, the European Commission (EC) adopted a Circular Economy Action Plan¹ to help accelerate Europe's transition towards a circular economy, boost global competitiveness, promote sustainable economic growth and generate new jobs. The action plan also identifies that the development of the Circular Economy (CE) will require public and private sources of financing to scale up improved technologies and processes, develop infrastructure and increase cooperation between actors in the value chain. Significant support for these objectives will come from EU funding programmes such as Horizon Europe, LIFE and IPA III; however, the private finance sector also needs to be directed towards new opportunities created by the CE.

This deliverable aims to investigate additional private and public funding opportunities that could be applied to the CE solutions addressed in ECOBULK project to enhance their implementation and deployment at a larger scale and scope.

The first part of this document establishes the background information about the private and public funding opportunities by looking at relevant public regional/national schemes and other private funding resources (e.g. foundations, professional associations and corporations).

This information is evaluated in the context of results obtained and exploitation opportunities identified in the project to create a plan for seeking additional funding. Having the exploitation opportunities identified by the partners in D8.2 as starting points, key concepts and ideas are selected and analysed for their continuity beyond ECOBULK with the same configuration or smaller partnership, at national or European level.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2015/EN/1-2015-614-EN-F1-1.PDF>

2. Funding landscape

2.1. *European* financial instruments supporting CE

The EC supports financially the transition towards CE through different financial streams, such as the European Structural and Investment Funds, Horizon Europe, the Instruments for Pre-accession Assistance, and the LIFE programme.² During the ECOBULK project, it has also been possible to apply for financing from pre-2020 instruments, such as Horizon 2020, COSME and InnovFin. In this document, the latter instruments are analysed in Appendix A whereas those which are ongoing and that could potentially support CE initiatives at the current stage of the project are detailed in this section.

2.1.1. Horizon Europe

Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation with a budget of 95.5 €billion. The main objectives of this program are to tackle climate change, achieve United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth. The structure of the programme implementing Horizon Europe for civil applications is based on three main pillars, as can be seen in Figure 1. Pillar 1 and 3 will mostly follow mono beneficiary schemes whereas grants under pillar 2 will be mostly to transnational consortium beneficiaries. For the continuation of actions started in the ECOBULK project, Pillar 2 is the most promising one, being the clusters including natural resources, energy and environment the most related to CE.

²https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls_en#esif

Figure 1: Horizon Europe structure³

From the total budget of Horizon Europe, Pillar 2 receives 53 516 million €, which are distributed as exposed in Table 1.

Table 1 Budget for Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness⁴

	Budget (€ million)
Clusters	52 546
Health	8 246
Culture, creativity and inclusive society	2 280
Civil security for Society	1 596
Digital, Industry and Space	15 349
Climate, Energy and Mobility	15 123
Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment	9 952
Non-nuclear direct actions of the Joint Research Centre (JCR)	1 970

Horizon Europe has already published open calls for beneficiaries and consortiums in the framework of the aforementioned clusters. From this first round of calls, some of the related with CE and which may be of interest to continue the developments carried out in ECOBULK are exposed in Table 2.

Table 2 Budget for Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness

Topic	Call	Type of action	Deadline
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³https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/strategy_on_research_and_innovation/presentations/horizon_europe/ec_rtd_he-investing-to-shape-our-future.pdf

⁴ Horizon Europe – the most ambitious EU research & innovation programme ever. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/1f107d76-acbe-11eb-9767-01aa75ed71a1>

Integrated solutions for circularity in buildings and the construction sector	HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-02-1-two-stage	Innovation	1 st stage: 15/02/2022 2 nd stage: 01/09/2022
Sustainable biodegradable novel bio-based plastics: innovation for sustainability and end-of-life options of plastics	HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-02-1-two-stage	Innovation	1 st stage: 15/02/2022 2 nd stage: 01/09/2022
Demonstration of innovative materials, supply cycles, recycling technologies to increase the overall circularity of wind energy technology and to reduce the primary use of critical raw materials	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01-02	Innovation	26/04/2022

2.1.2. European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF)

Over half of the EU budget is managed in partnership with national and regional authorities through a system of "shared management", largely through 5 big funds clustered under the umbrella of ESIF.⁵ These 5 funds are as follows:⁶

- **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)** – promotes balanced development in the different regions of the EU.
- **European Social Fund (ESF)** - supports employment-related projects throughout Europe and invests in Europe’s human capital – its workers, its young people and all those seeking a job.
- **Cohesion Fund (CF)** – funds transport and environment projects in countries where the gross national income (GNI) per inhabitant is less than 90% of the EU average. In 2021-27, these are Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia.
- **European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)** – focuses on resolving the particular challenges facing the EU's rural areas.
- **European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF)** – helps fishermen to adopt sustainable fishing practices and coastal communities to diversify their economies, improving quality of life along European coasts.

With their objective of promoting economic and social cohesion across the EU, the ERDF and the CF are the most relevant structural funds to assist the

⁵ https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/funding-grants_en

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes/overview-funding-programmes/european-structural-and-investment-funds_en

transition towards the circularity of EU Member States.⁷ The ERDF focuses its investments on several key priority areas, such as innovation and research, the digital agenda, support for SMEs and the low-carbon economy. Potential beneficiaries of ERDF are broad, including local, regional and national authorities and administrative bodies, NGOs, associations and foundations, enterprises and SMEs.⁸

The CF is also directed towards supporting the circular economy, including support for reuse and repair, improved production processes, product design and SMEs. The Commission will assist the Member States, regions and local authorities in strengthening their circular economy approach in this context through targeted outreach.⁹ Investment priorities for the CF are: supporting the shift towards a low-carbon economy in all sectors, promoting climate change adaptation, risk prevention and management, preserving and protecting the environment and promoting resources and sustainable transport and removing bottlenecks in key network infrastructures. Potential beneficiaries of the CF are all Member States with a Gross National Income less than 90 % of the EU average.⁶ In the funding period 2014-2020 this criterion is met by one country from the ECOBULK project, which is Portugal.

In general, resources available from the ESI Funds for the CE transition in years 2014-2020 distributes as follows:¹⁰

- €35 billion committed to the environment and resource efficiency
- That includes €5.5 billion for waste management:
 - €2.1 billion for prevention and recycling
 - €2.8 billion for incineration and thermal treatment
 - €0.6 billion for hazardous waste management

The resources for the 2021-2027 periods should be agreed upon between countries and the European Commission, which is a currently ongoing process. Additional funds may be channelled to the CE from the financial envelopes dedicated to the following:

- the competitiveness of SMEs
- low carbon economy
- network infrastructure in transport and energy

⁷ Houston et al., 2018. Stakeholder Views Report Enablers and Barriers to a Circular Economy. R2PiProject, available at: <http://www.r2piproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/R2pi-stakeholders-report-sept-2018.pdf>

⁸ Margaras, 2017. Guide to EU Funding 2014-2020. European Parliament, available at: http://www.europarl.europa.eu/EPRS/Funding_Guide.pdf

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2015/EN/1-2015-614-EN-F1-1.PDF>

¹⁰ Stuchtey et al., 2018. The Role of Business in the Circular Economy Markets, Processes and Enabling Policies. Report of the CEPS Task Force, available at: <https://www.ceps.eu/publications/role-business-circular-economy-markets-processes-and-enabling-policies>

A large part of ESI Funds consists of EU grants with national co-financing but other financial instruments are also available in some regions (e.g. loans, guarantees or equity financing).

2.1.3. Environment and climate action (LIFE)

The LIFE Programme is the EU's funding instrument supporting nature, the environment and quality of life in Europe's transition to a more sustainable and low-carbon future. It has been supporting projects relevant to the CE and resource efficiency since 1992 with over 670 waste reduction, recycling, and reuse projects, totalling over €1 billion of EU funding.¹¹ The current LIFE funding period 2021-2027 has a budget of 5 432 €million and is dedicated to four sub-programmes as exposed in Table 3.

Table 3 LIFE sub-programs and budget¹²

Sub-program	Budget (€million)
Nature and Biodiversity	2 143
Circular Economy and Quality of Life	1 345
Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation	947
Clean Energy Transition	997

Anyone registered in the EU can make a proposal for LIFE traditional, integrated, preparatory, and technical assistance projects, including public body operating under a national government's authority (e.g. local authority, national administration etc.), private commercial organisation and private non-commercial organisation (NGOs etc.). In contrast to other funding programmes, LIFE projects are very flexible in terms of how they are set up. They can be run by individual entities or by joining forces with partners from their own or another country.

2.1.4. Instruments for Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA III)

The Instruments for Pre-Accession Assistance have been renewed into IPA III, with a total budget of over 14 €billion for the 2021-2027 multiannual financial framework period. IPA III will provide support to Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Turkey. Of these countries, the one which has ECOBULK representation is Turkey.

IPA III can support investments in public administration reform, rule of law, sustainable economy, people and agriculture and rural development. Its support for economic development is diverse and depends on the countries' economic structure. Actions include preparing feasibility studies for loans from the International Financial Institutions, support to SMEs to improve

¹¹ <https://www.switchtogreen.eu/?p=846>

¹² Regulation (EU) 2021/783 of the European Parliament and of the council of 29 April 2021 establishing a Programme for the Environmental and Climate Action (LIFE), and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1293/2013

access to finance, setting up quality infrastructure agencies, and boosting the energy and transport infrastructure.

2.1.5. The Recovery and Resilience Facility

This financing instrument is key at the heart of NextGenerationEU to help the EU emerge stronger and more resilient from the current crisis. It allocates €723.8 billion in loans (€385.8€ billion) and grants (€338 billion) to support reforms and investments. It aims to mitigate the economic and social impact of the coronavirus pandemic and make European economies and societies more sustainable, resilient, and better prepared for upcoming challenges and opportunities. The facility, which entered in force in February 2021, will finance reforms and investments in Member States until December 2026. The funds from the Facility are employed according to the plans developed by Member States and approved by the commission.

2.1.6. Innovation Fund

The Innovation fund is focused on the demonstration of innovative low-carbon technologies. It will provide €20 billion of support over 2020-2030 for the commercial demonstration of innovative low-carbon technologies to bring to the market industrial solutions to decarbonise Europe and support its transition to climate neutrality¹³. Although this fund is not directly related to the promotion of circular economy, it is useful for some of the developments carried out in ECOBULK, especially in terms of efficiency increase in material's and product's production processes as well as the reduction of the environmental impact through recycling processes. The Innovation Fund will open calls for large and small-scale projects focusing on:

- Innovative low-carbon technologies and processes in energy-intensive industries, including products substituting carbon-intensive ones
- Carbon capture and utilization
- Construction and operation of carbon capture and storage
- Innovation renewable energy generation
- Energy storage

From these points, the one most interesting for ECOBULK purposes is the first one "Innovative low-carbon technologies and processes in energy-intensive industries including products substituting carbon-intensive ones".

2.1.7. European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT)

The EIT is a body created by the European Union in 2008 to strengthen Europe's ability to innovate. EIT is integrated into Pillar III of Horizon Europe and contributes to achieve four key strategic points:

¹³https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/innovation-fund_en

- Strengthening sustainable innovation ecosystems across Europe
- Fostering the development of entrepreneurial and innovation skills in a lifelong learning perspective and support the entrepreneurial transformation of EU universities
- Bringing new solutions to global societal challenges to the market
- Creating synergies and added value within Horizon Europe.

In the 2021-2027 period, EIT accounts with a budget of €3 billion euros to achieve these points¹⁴. One of the main activities of the EIT is the creation of communities dedicated to finding solutions to global challenges, from climate change and sustainable energy to healthy living and food. ECOBULK partners can benefit from these initiatives to connect with organisations or innovators with alike interests that could facilitate the creation of new circular economy initiatives. Specifically, EIT Digital, EIT Manufacturing and EIT Urban Mobility have recently presented a joint actions to promote circular economy across Europe¹⁵. This action includes two specific calls¹⁶:

- **Call on Environmental Technology Verification (ETV):** This call is open to any partner and start-up participating in the EIT community with a technology included in the areas of water treatment, material, waste and resources or energy.
- **Call on Circular SMEs:** The aim of this call is to enable the joint competencies and capacities of the EIT community to help solve a more systematic circularity in an orchestrated effort.

2.1.8. InvestEU

The InvestEU programme follows the Investment Plan for Europe and brings together under one roof the previous European Fund for Strategic Investment and 13 other EU financial instruments. It plans to trigger more than 372 €billion in investment over the period 2021-2027 and aims to give a boost to sustainable investment, innovation, and job creation in Europe.

The InvestEU consist of three main building blocks: InvestEU fund, InvestEU Advisory Hub and InvestEU Portal. This structure enables the creation of a solid framework for the connexion of investors and project promoters, the preparation of investment projects and access to finance.

The InvestEU fund supports 4 policy windows:

- **Sustainable infrastructure:** Sustainable energy, digital connectivity, transport, circular economy, water, waste, and other environmental infrastructure.
- **Research, innovation and digitalization:** Research and innovation, taking research results to the market, digitalization of

¹⁴<https://eit.europa.eu/who-we-are/eit-glance/eit-strategy-2021-2027>

¹⁵<https://www.eitmanufacturing.eu/what-we-do/cross-kic-transversal-activities/circular-economy/>

¹⁶<https://eit.europa.eu/news-events/news/eit-community-launches-joint-circular-economy-calls>

industry, scaling up to larger innovative companies, artificial intelligence and more.

- **Small and medium-sized companies (SMEs):** Facilitating access to finance for SMEs.
- **Social investment and skills:** Skills, education, training, social housing, schools, universities, hospitals, social innovation, healthcare, long-term care and accessibility, microfinance, social enterprise, integration of migrants, refugees and vulnerable people.

The Sustainable infrastructure policy window can be employed to boost ECOBULK outcomes on circular economy and waste. As InvestEU plays a critical role in achieving the objectives stated in the Green Deal, at least 30% of the InvestEU programme shall support financing for investment that contributes to the EU's climate objectives. Moreover, 60% of the investments supported under the "Sustainable Infrastructure Window" of the InvestEU fund shall contribute to the EU's climate and environmental objectives.¹⁷

2.1.9. European Investment Bank (EIB)

In light of the EC Circular Economy Package, the EIB, as the EU bank, aims to support the transition to a CE, in particular in the EU, but also in other parts of the world. While the EIB has a long track record of lending to projects focusing on recycling and the recovery of waste and by-products in various sectors, there is room for expanding the lending volume to innovative CE projects aimed at systematically designing out waste, extending the life of assets and closing material loops.¹⁸

The EIB allocated approximately €2.4 billion in co-financing for circular projects over the period 2013-2018:¹⁹

- €680 million in lending for industry and service
- €640 million for water management
- €530 million for agriculture and the bio-economy
- €360 million for waste management
- €170 million for product-to-service

Special activities run by the EIB in partnership with other institutions may also play a role, such as:

¹⁷ https://europa.eu/investeu/contribution-green-deal-and-just-transition-scheme_en

¹⁸ <https://www.resourceefficient.eu/en/support-programme/european-investment-bank-funding-circular-economy-projects>

¹⁹ Stuchtey et al., 2018. The Role of Business in the Circular Economy Markets, Processes and Enabling Policies. Report of the CEPS Task Force, available at: <https://www.ceps.eu/publications/role-business-circular-economy-markets-processes-and-enabling-policies>

- Green Bonds (Climate Awareness Bonds), which raised over €15 billion in a decade to finance over 60 projects with a strong environmental impact.
- The Marguerite Fund II with €200 million committed to fund transport, energy, renewable energy, energy efficiency, ICT and water treatment.

The EIB has a range of financing products and instruments that are well adapted to support the transition to the CE. Financing can be tailored to the specific needs of the borrower and the project reflecting that investment needs vary widely depending on a project's scale, maturity, type of promoter, position in the value chain, etc. For more traditional and larger scale CE projects requiring loans higher than 25 €million, the EIB offers medium and long-term direct loans with fixed or variable interest rates. For smaller operations, the EIB offers financing indirectly through credit lines to local banks and other intermediaries, particularly targeting SMEs and mid-caps. More information about EIB's standard lending products can be found on the website.²⁰

The EIB also offers CE advisory services, and is active in CE networking, sharing of best practices, connecting different CE stakeholders and facilitating access to CE finance. Finally, the EIB has developed a Circular Economy Guide²¹ that aims to promote a common understanding of the CE concept and related challenges and opportunities among the financial and project partners, raise awareness about and promote circular solutions among project promoters and other stakeholders, facilitate and harmonise due diligence of and reporting on CE projects by the financial and project partners, communicate the vision of how the EIB can further support the transition to a CE. The Guide is a living document that will be updated in response to the evolving understanding of CE needs, opportunities and risks, and growing experience with the appraisal and financing of CE projects.²²

Financial support is available to all industries and sectors, to all types of companies and organisations and for all EU countries.

2.1.10. Public contracts

The European Commission uses public contracts to buy services, works and goods from the market for its internal use. They are not considered a form of EU funding, but, accounting for a significant part of overall demand for goods and services, public procurement could therefore be utilised as a

²⁰ <https://www.eib.org/en/products/lending/>

²¹ European Investment Bank, 2019. The EIB Circular Economy Guide. Supporting the circular transition. Available at:
https://www.eib.org/attachments/thematic/circular_economy_guide_en.pdf

²² <https://www.resourceefficient.eu/en/support-programme/european-investment-bank-funding-circular-economy-projects>

major demand-side policy instrument for the creation of markets for more environmentally friendly products and services. At the EU level, it is estimated that public procurement annually accounts for about 14% of EU GDP in expenditure.²³

Public procurement can therefore play a key role in the CE, and the Commission will encourage this role through its actions on Green Public Procurement (GPP), where criteria are developed at the EU level and then used by public authorities voluntarily. The European Commission will make sure that in future, special emphasis is placed on aspects relevant to the CE, such as durability and reparability when setting out or revising criteria. Secondly, it will support greater uptake of these criteria by public authorities and reflect on how GPP could be used more widely across the EU, in particular for products or markets that have high relevance for the CE.²⁴

2.2. Support of CE at the national/regional level

In addition to the European Instruments supporting CE, Governments' interventions also play an important role in setting directions towards the CE. These local initiatives are more dynamic and follow closely the evolution of countries' society and the developments needed to achieve a successful CE. Examples of initiatives to foster CE in countries where ECOBULK has a representation are exposed in Table 4. In the following pages, the most significant of these initiatives are explained in more detail.

Table 4 Examples of CE supporting instruments in different European countries where the ECOBULK consortium is present

Country	ECOBULK partners	Instruments supporting CE initiatives
United Kingdom	Oakdene Hollins, Netcomposites, Microcab, Cranfield University, Ansys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovate UK • Knowledge Transfer Network (KTN) • Waste and Resources Action Programme (WRAP) • Zero Waste Scotland • Innovation Centres • Scottish Institute for Remanufacture (SIR) • Catapult Centres • Plastics Research and Innovation Fund
Spain	ITENE, UPC, Maier, IRIS,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • España Circular 2030 • I Plan de Acción de Economía Circular

²³ Stuchtey et al., 2018. The Role of Business in the Circular Economy Markets, Processes and Enabling Policies. Report of the CEPS Task Force, available at: <https://www.ceps.eu/publications/role-business-circular-economy-markets-processes-and-enabling-policies>

²⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2015/EN/1-2015-614-EN-F1-1.PDF>

	KNEIA, UNE, Aimplas, Bellver	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan Estatal Marco de Gestión de Residuo 2016 - 2022 (PEMAR 2016 - 2022) • Estrategia Española de Bioeconomía Horizonte 2030 • Estrategia Estatal de Infraestructura Verde Conectividad y Restauración Ecológicas - EEIVCRE • Estrategia Andaluza de Bioeconomía (Andalucía) • La Estratègia d'impuls a l'economia verda i a l'Economia Circular (Catalunya) • IV Plan Ambiental del País Vasco (Basque Country)
Italy	CNR, CRF, NTT, Technoplants, Moretti Compact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Guarantee Funds (e.g Marguerite Fund II, Fondo Rotativo Imprese, EEEF fund) • National and regional funding and policy measures (e.g. States-General of the Green Economy, Symbiosis Users Network, Start to be circular (Milan), Lazio Green) • "Green" public procurement of goods and services (National Action Plan on Green Public Procurement) • National Operational Programme (NOP)
Germany	Tecnaro, Tomra	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource Efficient Circular Economy— Innovative Product Cycles initiative • German Resource Efficiency Programme (ProgRes II) • Waste prevention Programme • National High-Tech Strategy • Central Innovation Programme for SMEs • Framework Programme for Research for Sustainable Development
France	FCBA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Transition Accelerator • Ecotechnologies Fund • Green Tech • ADEME • Fond Unique Interministerie (FUI) • Fond Dechets/R&D programmes
Sweden	AkzoNobel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Investment Fund • Almi Invest GreenTech • Vinnova • Business Sweden • Almi • The National Agency for Public

		Procurement
Portugal	Lipor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundo Ambiental • The FITEC fund • National Science Foundation (FCT)
Finland	Conenor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finnvera • Finnish Industry Investment (FII) • Business Finland • Academy of Finland • Invest in Finland • The Finnish Innovation Fund (SITRA) • Finnish municipalities and regional development companies
Netherlands	TU Delft ISWA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dutch Research Council (NWO) • The Netherlands Enterprise Agency • Circular Procurement Green Deal • VAMIL/MIA • KIEM-VANG 2 • Innovation Credit
Turkey	KEAS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clean Technology Fund (CTF) • The Environment Protection and Packing Waste Recovery and Recycling Foundation (ÇEVKO) • Innovative Sustainability Solutions Contest • Turkey Materials Marketplace (TMM) • Ministry of Finance • Turkish Standards Institution

2.2.1. United Kingdom

Efforts in the UK in the areas of eco-innovation and the CE are actively promoted by the UK Government, the devolved administrations of Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland, Innovate UK, the Knowledge Transfer Network, WRAP and the Catapult Centres. Actions mainly evolve around four key areas:

- sustainable resources;
- rationale use of natural resources and critical materials;
- low carbon transport, focusing in particular on ultra-low emission vehicles; and,
- clean and carbon abatement technologies.

These areas and sectors have continuously grown over the past few years and significantly shape the UK's eco-innovation and CE profile. All key national instruments promoting the CE in the UK are as follows:²⁵

²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/united-kingdom_en

- **Innovate UK** is the UK's innovation agency, which was founded "to find and drive the science and technology innovations that will help the UK economy grow". Since 2007, Innovate UK has invested more than £2.2 billion in innovation and helped more than 8,000 organisations to develop projects estimated to add £16 billion to the UK economy and create 70,000 new jobs. Innovate UK offer various other funding streams which are open to any innovations, regardless of industry, and we are confident that these funding streams will help any truly game-changing technology to develop and flourish.
- Funded by Innovate UK, the **Knowledge Transfer Network (KTN)** contributes to eco-innovation in the UK, with 16 focus areas including Biosciences (agriculture, food and industrial bioscience sectors) Energy, Sustainability & Resources Efficiency, Built Environment and Transport. Innovate UK and the KTN share the belief that innovation is more successful when leveraged by collaboration. The KTN adds value by identifying where the knowledge is in the UK economy and linking it between complementary actors such as academics, businesses and manufacturers for the most innovative ideas to emerge and to materialise.
- **The Waste and Resources Action Programme (WRAP)** provides advice and support to businesses, consumers and public agencies to address innovation, resource and waste challenges in products and supply chains. Its objective is to minimise resource use, divert materials from landfills and create a market for recycled materials. WRAP operates in England, Wales (WRAP Cymru) and Northern Ireland.
- **Zero Waste Scotland** is funded by the Scottish Government to promote a society where resources are valued and nothing is wasted. Their mission is to influence and enable change – from gathering evidence and informing policy, to motivating practical behaviour change in individuals and organisations. They also make direct interventions to affect change, commonly in the form of finance, business support, technical advice, training and competence development or communications support. As Scotland's Circular Economy expert, they are supporting delivery of the Scottish Government's CE Strategy – Making Things Last – and work with a range of partner organisations to enable businesses, consumers and householders to understand and implement CE practices.
- Eight **Innovation Centres** have been set up in Scotland of which two are of particular interest in the sphere of eco-innovation – the Construction Scotland Innovation Centre (CSIC) and the Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre (IBioIC). Since launching in October 2014, CSIC's industry-led team have been linking together businesses, university experts and public sector providers including Scottish Enterprise and Scottish Development International to support businesses to deliver transformational change in construction. IBioIC's role, as a specialist in the Industrial Biotechnology (IB) sector, is to stimulate the growth of the IB sector in Scotland to £900 million by 2025. IBioIC connects industry,

academia and government and facilitates collaborations, provides scale-up capabilities, creates networks and develops skills.

- **The Scottish Institute for Remanufacture (SIR)** brings together businesses with academic partners to stimulate and drive remanufacturing projects, addressing industry challenges to increase innovation in remanufacturing. This institute is one of four global centres of excellence in remanufacturing.
- **The Catapult Centres** are not-for-profit, independent technology and innovation centres connecting businesses of all sizes with the UK's research and academic communities. This network with its overall large-scale investments in innovation research plays a strong role in eco-innovation activities and in bridging the gap between business, academia, research and government.

Progress has been made over the past few years in terms of waste recycling, driven by EU legislation, such as the EC Waste Framework Directive, EC Waste Statistics Regulation, EC Landfill Directive and EC Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive. The UK Government has announced a strategy to combat the UK's growing waste problem.²⁶ This strategy will result in businesses and manufacturers having to pay the full cost of recycling or disposing of their packaging waste. This will transform the waste system by putting more ownership on the companies that produce damaging waste. A funding opportunity arising from this strategy is **The Plastics Research and Innovation Fund (PRIF)**. In this fund, £20 million was pledged to the PRIF (co-ordinated by Innovate UK and EPSRC), which aims to reduce the environmental costs of plastic and litter. Funded activities will be focused on developing solutions to reduce plastics entering the environment, funding for smart waste tracking data collection, storage and reporting services, for smart local energy systems, and for technology that advances the UK's low carbon automotive capability.

2.2.2. Spain

Public policy support for the CE in Spain is a mix of first and second-generation policies and measures addressing technologies and resources for pollution control and energy efficiency. The circular economy and eco-innovation are generally embedded in national and regional policies targeting resource efficiency, environmental innovations, clean technologies and sustainable development. In February 2018, the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and environment released the **first Spanish Strategy on Circular Economy (Estrategia Española de Economía Circular)**²⁷ to promote the shift towards a model of CE in the country. Related to this is the Pact for a Circular Economy: the compromise of the

²⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/resources-and-waste-strategy-for-england>

²⁷ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/prensa/ultimas-noticias/el-gobierno-aprueba-el-i-plan-de-acci%C3%B3n-de-econom%C3%ADa-circular-con-un-presupuesto-de-1.529-millones-de-euros/tcm:30-526709>

economic and social agents 2018 – 2020 that was signed by more than 300 stakeholders in September 2017. The aim is to involve the most relevant economic and social agents of Spain to make the shift in the system. The strategy includes an action plan for the period 2018-2020 that required an investment of €834 million. The action plan focused on five priority sectors, such as building, agriculture, industry, consumer goods and tourism. Within these sectors, the Plan's actions raised eight major lines, that included: production, which allocated €31.7 million; consumption, €20 million; waste management, €28.5 million; secondary raw materials, €997,362; water reuse, €478.2 million; research, innovation and competitiveness, €241 million; awareness and participation, €553,883, and employment and training, €36.6 million. Following this Strategy on Circular Economy, the strategy **Circular Spanish 2030 (España Circular 2030)**²⁸ was launched in 2021 with the same eight actuation lines and which aimed to further promote circular economy to achieve sustainable development goals, green delay and agenda 2030 objectives. In this framework, the Spanish government recently approved the first action plan for circular economy (**I Plan de Acción en Economía Circular**) with a budget of 1 529 €million. This plan is focused on the first three years of Circular Spanish 2030, from 2021 to 2023, aiming to progressively consolidate the circular and decarbonised energy model in society. This action plan includes initiatives such as SMEs circular (**PYME Circular**) which supports the integration of CE in SMEs and the creation of new business models, the introduction of new products label including information on lifetime and re-manufacturability indices, and an entrepreneur programme (**Programa Eprendeverde**) to foster innovation, research, and competitiveness in the field of CE.²⁹

Environmental sustainability also plays a very important role on the funding R&D strategies, with programmes such as PTAS (Programa Tecnológico de Automoción Sostenible, 40M€ budget in 2021) where sustainable mobility and zero emissions of the automotive industry are two of its main goals, and Misiones Ciencia e Innovación (141,25M€ budget) where circular economy of polymers is one of the 9 topics.

Other CE strategies including, among others, waste prevention, waste management, bio-economy and green and circular economy are available at both national and regional levels. Examples of these are the **Plan Estatal Marco de Gestión de Residuo 2016 - 2022 (PEMAR 2016 – 2022)**, **Estrategia Española de Bioeconomía Horizonte 2030**, **Estrategia Estatal de Infraestructura Verde Conectividad y Restauración Ecológicas – EEIVCRE**, **Estrategia Andaluza de Bioeconomía (Andalucía)**, **La Estratègia d'impuls a l'economia verda i a l'Economia**

²⁸ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/temas/economia-circular/estrategia/>

²⁹ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/planes-y-estrategias/Planes-y-Programas.aspx#ancla4>

Circular (Cataluna) **and IV Plan Ambiental del País Vasco** (Basque Country).^{30 31}

2.2.3. Italy

In November 2017, The Italian government published a strategic paper on the promotion of the CE in the country, outlining its commitment to the efficient use of resources paired with support for sustainable consumption practices. The document, entitled “**Verso un Modello di Economia Circolare per l’Italia**” (Towards a Circular Economy Model in Italy)³², was created by the Ministry of the Environment and the Ministry of Economic Development and is part of the broader national strategy for sustainable development. It proposes a paradigm shift, where steps to improve sustainability can be taken from both the supply and demand side of the economy. The paper stresses the obligation of manufacturers to take responsibility for the full lifecycle of the product, inviting business actors to come together and develop consortia to manage waste. Also, environmental communication plans need to raise awareness among consumers to trigger new consumption models, such as repairing instead of replacing, sharing over ownership, and recycling.

Apart from that, below is a list of selected good practices of policy measures and initiatives from national, regional or local government on resource efficiency and CE:³³

- Public guarantee funds –
 - **Marguerite Fund II**: CDP, EIB and the principal Promotion National Institutes (BGK, CDC, KfW and ICO) launched in 2017 the successor fund of Marguerite I: €700 million for projects in sustainable infrastructures.
 - **Fondo Rotativo Imprese**: a revolving fund that supports research and innovation projects, with the participation of the Ministry of Economic Development, ABI and CDP. In 2017, €75 million have been released for the industrial sustainability target.
 - **EEEF fund** managed by “Cassa depositi e prestiti”, which is funded by the EC and EIB, among others. It funds local authorities, utilities, public transport operators, and ESCOs. It amounts to €800 million.
- **National and regional funding and policy measures – national R&D tenders published the Ministry of Environment** - e.g. €1.2 million to finance industrial research and/or experimental development to encourage products eco-design and correct waste

³⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/spain_en

³¹ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/planes-y-estrategias/Planes-y-Programas.aspx#ancla4>

³² https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/sites/default/files/strategy_-_towards_a_model_eng_completo.pdf

³³ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/italy_en

management; €0.9 million tenders to increase the technological level of treatment plants, to maximise the quantity of recoverable or recyclable material.

- **States-General of the Green Economy** - multi-stakeholder process, promoted by the National Council of the green economy, composed of 66 business organisations, in collaboration with the Ministry of Environment and the Ministry of Economic Development.
- **Symbiosis Users Network** - an Italian industrial symbiosis network promoting eco-innovation and the transition to the circular economy through the application of industrial symbiosis.
- **Start to be circular** (Milan municipality) - an initiative of the municipality of Milan promoted by the Bracco Foundation, the Giuseppina Mai Foundation of Confindustria and Banca Prossima, created to promote the transition to sustainable growth through innovative entrepreneurial initiatives.
- **"Green" public procurement of goods and services** – The Green Public Procurement (GPP) National Action Plan (NAP) document³⁴ outlines the strategy for the diffusion of GPP in Italy, the commodity categories, the reference environmental targets to be attained - both qualitative and quantitative - and the general methodological aspects. Moreover, from 2016, the Law n.221 of 28 of December 2015, established the compulsory commitment for the Italian Public Administration to the GPP. Italy thus became the first country in the world to adopt such an obligation.
- **National Operational Programme (NOP)** – supporting research, technological development and innovation

2.2.4. Germany

In January 2017, the Federal Government approved an updated Sustainable Development Strategy³⁵, which is the most extensive enhancement of the Strategy since its first adoption in 2002. It presents Germany's measures to implement the 17 SDGs (including Goal 12 Sustainable consumption and production) at three levels and contains 63 "key indicators", mostly associated with quantified targets.

The German government strategy has set the goal of conserving natural resources and increasing total raw material productivity in Germany by 30% by 2030 compared to 2010. One of the government's programs to achieve this is the **Resource Efficient Circular Economy—Innovative Product Cycles initiative** which provides grants over the period 2019–2022 to collaborative projects that focus on innovative product designs that lower

³⁴ <https://www.minambiente.it/pagina/piano-dazione-nazionale-sul-gpp>

³⁵

<https://www.bundesregierung.de/resource/blob/975274/1588964/1b24acbed2b731744c2ffa4ca9f3a6fc/2019-03-13-dns-aktualisierung-2018-englisch-data.pdf?download=1>

environmental impacts and costs across the life cycle, as well as enable subsequent repair and upgrades.³⁶

Examples of other programmes and measures supporting resource efficiency and CE in Germany are:³⁷

- **German Resource Efficiency Programme (ProgRes II)** - in 2012 the German government adopted the ProgRes Resource Efficiency Programme which aims to strive for more sustainable use of natural resources and the reduction of any adverse impacts on the environment. Measures include improving the efficiency of consulting for SMEs, support for environmental management systems, the increased procurement of resource-efficient products and consumer information as well as a stronger technology and transfer of knowledge to developing countries and improved services by the public sector.
- **Waste Prevention Programme** – following the introduction of the Waste Management Act in 2012, the Federal Cabinet adopted the first German Waste Prevention Programme, which comprehensively introduces and promotes waste prevention approaches, such as the reuse of products, the design of minimal-waste products, and the extension of the life span of products. Along with information policy, awareness-raising and support of R&D, the Waste Prevention Programme pursues further objectives, such as the support of the EU Ecodesign Directive, organisational and financial support of reuse and multiple uses of products, repair centres, encouraging a more intensive use of commodities by a larger group of users (such as car-sharing), minimise food waste at every stage of the production and supply chain, and the extension of the Blue Angel scheme to widen the range of product groups, etc.
- **National High-Tech Strategy** - strategy on innovation policy to systematically support priority fields (e.g. digital economy and society, sustainable economy and energy, innovative working, healthy living, intelligent mobility and civil security). The High-Tech Strategy introduced new instruments such as the innovation alliances –strategic long-term cooperation between industry and public research in key technology areas that require strong funding.
- **Central Innovation Programme for SMEs** – designed to increase the innovative capacity and competitiveness of SMEs willing to develop new or significantly improve existing products, processes technical services.
- **Framework Programme for Research for Sustainable Development** – design to support any activities contributing to a sustainable economy that is both competitive and environmentally friendly at the global scale.

³⁶ <https://medium.com/mark-and-focus/germanys-2022-circular-economy-214b7ad8470f>

³⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/germany_en

As an example of good practice at the regional level, The Federal State of Bremen provides subsidies for investments to build a pioneering environmentally friendly recycling and disposal infrastructure, as well as for projects that comply with the prevention principle aspired in the recycling and waste management act.

2.2.5. France

In February 2018, the French government presented the first draft of the roadmap for the CE³⁸ that tackles waste management, product eco-conception, consumption, the financial means needed for the transition towards the CE, and the stakeholders involved. The roadmap contains five main objectives:

- reduce by 30% the resource use and consumption compared to the GDP until 2030, compared to 2010;
- reduce by half the amount of non-hazardous waste in landfills in 2025, compared to 2010;
- recycle 100% of the plastic waste in 2025;
- reduce GHG emissions through plastic waste recycling; and,
- create 300,000 new jobs.

The following examples of policy measures addressing the CE have been adopted in France:³⁹

- **Green Transition Accelerator** – is a think-tank that aims at uniting the economic actors (enterprises, training centres, social partners) to support employment and innovations, to enhance green growth. It will work on eco renovations, renewable energies, circular economy and adapting ecological taxation to the challenges of the transition and development of green finance.
- **Ecotechnologies Fund** – this €150 million fund invests (between €1m and €10m) in innovative SMEs that cover the following areas: new renewable energies, green chemistry, circular economy, smart grids, vehicles of the future.
- **Green Tech** – is a national incubator for start-ups, targeting ICT-enabled eco-innovations.
- **ADEME** - is responsible for guiding, scheduling and coordinating research in its areas of action: energy and climate; sustainable consumption, waste and material management; sustainable land management and preservation and remediation of environments (soil and air).
- **Fond Unique Interministeriel (FUI)** – involves industries and SMEs in particular in collaborative projects. Projects should be labelled by a French competitive pole and involve at least 2 SMEs and an RTD.

³⁸ <https://www.ecologique-solidaire.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/FREC%20anglais.pdf>

³⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/france_en

- **Fonds Dechets/ R&D Programmes** – supports the investment of equipment for recycling valorization and to increase the maturity of innovative technologies.

2.2.6. Sweden

The Swedish policy landscape provides the following examples of instruments supporting the transition to the CE:⁴⁰

- **Green Investment Fund** – provides funding for early-stage research projects.
- **Almi Invest GreenTech** - is an investment fund that is financed partly by the government and partly by EU funds. Its focus is on start-ups in GreenTech. The fund has SEK650 million at its disposal.
- **Vinnova** - Sweden's innovation agency has a budget of approximately SEK3 billion to invest in projects each year.
- **Business Sweden** - is the official investment promotion agency of Sweden. Business Sweden (formerly Invest Sweden) connects international companies with business opportunities in Sweden and offer comprehensive, one-stop investment consultancy services free of charge.
- **Almi** - is owned by the state with the task to promote the development of competitive small and medium-sized businesses as well as to stimulate new enterprises to create growth and innovation in Swedish business life.
- **The National Agency for Public Procurement** - gives support through consultation, practical tools and methods within the area of public procurement in general. The agency puts extra emphasis on environmentally friendly procurement as an instrument to achieve the policy objectives in the environmental area.

2.2.7. Portugal

Only recently Portugal has introduced **Fundo Ambiental**, which was created by the Decree-Law n.º 42-A/2016, replacing several other funding instruments, to support the implementation of environmental policies to pursue the sustainable development goals, to help achieve the national and international objectives, namely concerning climate change, water resources, waste management and nature and biodiversity conservation. The strategic coordination of the Fundo Ambiental falls on the Ministry of Environment and Climatic Action, which determines by Ministerial Order the yearly allocation of available funds. In 2017, the first year with the Fundo Ambiental was in full operation, several CE projects were supported through open calls in key areas. In 2021, the total funds allocated for waste and circular economy are 1 245 €thousand. Other examples of public measures addressing CE in Portugal are as follows:⁴¹

⁴⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/sweden_en

⁴¹ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/portugal_en

- **The FITEC fund** – with the main focus is to provide a public guarantee to the CE and eco-innovation related projects, helping these projects obtain lower financing costs.
- **National Science Foundation (FCT)** – with the aim to supports the scientific community in Portugal through a range of funding schemes, tailored for individual scientists, research teams or R&D centres.

2.2.8. Finland

Finland's public support regarding the CE is generally strong. Finland's ambition is to become a global leader in the CE by 2025, which is embedded in the country's climate change act⁴² which came into force in June 2015. Examples of instruments supporting CE include:⁴³

- **Finnvera** - is the official export credit agency for Finland. It offers loans, credits and guarantees for companies interested in eco-innovation and related investments.
- **Finnish Industry Investment (FII)** - is a government-owned venture capital and private equity company, with a focus on cleantech and mining.
- **Business Finland** - is the principal governmental funding body for both scientific research and applied developments and combines direct funding with grants and loans, especially in R&D. It grants funding and subsidies for the development of products, services and processes that are following sustainable development in general. Business Finland's funding specifically concerns innovation – transforming research-stage ideas (also those from universities and research institutes) into viable businesses.
- **Academy of Finland** - is a governmental funding body for scientific research. The Academy has funded several projects and researchers on topics related to energy and the environment.
- **Invest in Finland** - helps to promote different industries and technologies, including cleantech services and trade (e.g. Cleantech).
- **Finnish municipalities and Regional development companies** - work in close operation with governmental organisations and local companies in supporting start-ups to facilitate growth and new sustainable businesses.
- **The Finnish Innovation Fund (Sitra)** - promotes public discussion and informs consumers about the carbon-neutral CE and publishes reports and methodologies on how to put circular economy into practice

2.2.9. Netherlands

The Dutch Cabinet presented the plans of the government on the CE in September 2016 in the Government-wide program "**A Circular Economy**

⁴² https://www.ym.fi/en-US/The_environment/Climate_and_air/Mitigation_of_climate_change/National_climate_policy

⁴³ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/finland_en

in the Netherlands by 2050”. ⁴⁴ The programme acknowledges that both the economic structure and the material streams must change to change to the CE, which requires technical, social and systems innovations. Examples of other initiatives supporting CE in the Netherlands are as follow:

- **The Netherlands Enterprise Agency** – provides various research subsidy programmes also in the area of the CE.
- **Circular Procurement Green Deal** – Green Deals are non-financial support actions to create conditions for innovation and new sustainable entrepreneurial activities. Forty-five participants of the Green Deal Circular Procurement brought together their knowledge and experiences. With the Circular Procurement Green Deal public and private parties together performed almost 80 pilot projects.
- **VAMIL/MIA** - fiscal support schemes for green investments. On top of regular tax deductions for investments, organisations can deduct up to 36% of the investment costs for an environmentally friendly investment through the Environmental investment rebate (MIA). The Arbitrary depreciation of environmental investments (Vamil) can be used to write off sustainable investment costs in the years of your choice. All entrepreneurs can use these rules, as long as their investments are on the Environment list that has been made, which includes around 270 investments.
- **KIEM-VANG 2** – finances small targeted research projects which focus on applied research for the transition to CE. The scheme aims at closing some material chains, prevention of waste and simulation high-quality material. Additionally, cooperation between SMEs, research organisations and governments is developed.
- **Innovation Credit** – to provide SMEs with financial support for risky innovation projects.

Aside from these specific CE initiatives, the Dutch Research Council (NWO) invest each year almost €1 billion euros in curiosity-driven research, research related to societal challenges and research infrastructure. It selects and funds research proposals based on recommendations from expert scientists and other experts in Netherlands and abroad. For the period 2019-2022, a strategy plan has been created named “Connecting Science and Society”. In this plan, NWO emphasises its connecting role and formulates five main ambitions:

- Nexus: Connecting agendas, science and society
- People: Perspective for researchers
- Research: Collaboration for excellence and innovation
- Infrastructure: Accessible and sustainable scientific infrastructure
- Knowledge sharing: Effective use of knowledge through co-design and co-creation.

⁴⁴ <https://www.government.nl/documents/policy-notes/2016/09/14/a-circular-economy-in-the-netherlands-by-2050>

2.2.10. Turkey

The CE is still a new concept in Turkey, although some instruments supporting circular economy have been adopted in recent years, such as: ⁴⁵

- **Clean Technology Fund (CTF) combined with EBRD lending** – recently released the Near Zero Waste Programme (NØW), which is a strategic initiative to promote waste minimisation and pollution prevention projects in various sectors of the economy in Turkey. It will finance waste recycling infrastructure, biomass and biogas facilities, technologies that reduce packaging waste, and the use of alternative fuels in energy-intensive industries. The programme is expected to fund up to 12 investments for up to US\$ 125 million in total.
- **The Environment Protection and Packing Waste Recovery and Recycling Foundation (ÇEVKO)** - is a follower of the New Plastics Economy model, an initiative by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, the European Commission's "Circular Economy Package. the ÇEVKO foundation aims to set up an action plan for Turkey, together with NGOs and the public and industrial sector. the foundation contributed 2.6 billion Turkish Liras to the economy in 2017, thanks to the recycling efforts conducted together with industrial and local administrations.
- **Innovative Sustainability Solutions Contest** - was launched in 2013, and it is organized biennially. The contest rewards valuable sustainability solutions. This event's purpose is to emphasize the importance of innovation for the industry and to highlight good practices and make them widespread. The jury of the contest consists of stakeholders who are experts in public or private sectors, NGOs, academia or media. As a result of the assessment made by the jury, awards are granted in "Environmental", "Social" and "Economic" Innovative Solutions branches in "Large Company" and "SME" categories.
- **Turkey Materials Marketplace (TMM)** - aims to create a closed-loop, collaborative network of businesses, organizations and entrepreneurs where one organization's hard-to-recycle waste and by-products become another organization's raw material. The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) has launched the Circular Vouchers Scheme to provide technical support to the company members of the TMM in developing material exchanges transactions. The Circular Vouchers are funded by the EU's IPA 2013, to support energy and resource efficiency in Turkey.

Also, circular economy initiatives in Turkey are directly supported by the Ministry of Finance and the Turkish Standards Institution.

⁴⁵ <http://www.skdturkiye.org/en/surdurulebilir-sanayi-ve-dongusel-ekonomi>

2.3. Private financial opportunities supporting CE initiatives

To boost the transition towards the CE, it is important that public funding is supported by private institutions investing in circular and innovative ideas and technologies. Financial institutions and banks are the main funding bodies providing private capital to organisations to help them grow and achieve their strategic objectives. There are two main types of financing for companies: debt and equity. While debt needs to be repaid, equity does not require to be paid back, but it relinquishes ownership to the shareholders. Companies can use a combination of both to finance operations. Private financing organisations, such as banks, tend to avoid early-stage activities where risks are high and return uncertain. However, for projects and technologies that are close to the market, loans could be the most suitable instrument for raising the required capital.

The EIB (the European Investment Bank and the European Investment Fund) conducts an initiative in the circular economy domain by providing finance and advisory for CE projects. Apart from the EU EIB, there is a growing number of private green banks declaring the importance and support of circular entrepreneurship and innovation. For example, three large banks in the Netherlands (ABN-AMRO, Rabobank and ING) released a joint statement supporting the CE initiatives. They will also investigate what else is necessary to increase the knowledge of financial products and risk management in light of the CE. In France, the Banque Publique d'Investissement (Bpifrance) provides a green loan (Prêt Vert) for up to €3 million over seven years to SMEs investing in the CE at a subsidised interest rate, with no guarantees made against company assets. In Germany, Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) offers low-interest-rate loans, with some repayment bonus, via lending banks to small businesses for investments in energy-efficient production systems, using industrial waste heat, heat recovery systems, and more. Along with Germany's nonprofit Sparkassen banks, KfW has largely funded the country's green energy revolution. In Italy, Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP) wants to stimulate the sustainable development of the Italian economy – with several components directly relevant to Italian SMEs.

Private financing can also be provided by other organisations with business interests, including venture capital, business angels, incubators, foundations, professional associations and corporations. For early-stage projects and high-risk innovation, business angels can play an important role in exploring the potential of new ideas, even at the pilot/demonstration phase. Venture capital provides access to financing and managerial guidance when other sources of financing are not available.⁴⁶ Some examples of other private institutions supporting the CE initiatives are as follows:

⁴⁶ http://www.futuring-project.eu/static/deliverables/FUTURING_D3.4.pdf

- **Circularity Capital** – the company invests in innovative and market-leading businesses that create value from a defined range of circular activities: product-to-product, product-to-service, a waste product, circular design and enabling data solutions. Circularity Capital seeks to identify SMEs operating in Europe that require £1m - £5m of equity investment.⁴⁷
- **Funding Circle** – one of the best-capitalised lending platforms in the world and listed on the London Stock Exchange (Ticker: FCH) in October 2018. They have raised approximately £550 million since 2010 from some of the largest and most sophisticated investors around.⁴⁸
- **Kickstarter** – a crowdfunding platform.⁴⁹
- **Sustainable Accelerator** - venture capitalists investing in sustainable start-ups.⁵⁰
- **Fifo Capital** – a leading provider of business finance solutions for corporations through to SME's.⁵¹ The company opened in New Zealand and Australia but recently expanded also into the UK.

The exploitation of intellectual property rights, such as patents, licences, technology transfer and copyrights by third parties may also be a source of additional funding close to the market technologies.

2.4. Combined CE funding opportunities

In addition to public and private funding, a combined instrument (e.g. the Public-Private Partnership) is also considered a very important measure to accelerate the CE uptake. Combined public and private funds are a mix of various public and/or private financial instruments. The advantage of public-private funds is that the risk for a potential private investor is reduced, which may thus bring more capital for a given investment. Public funding acts as leverage to attract more funding coming from private sources.

A good example of the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) relevant for the CE is the **Sustainable Process Industry (SPIRE)** created by the European Commission together with eight sectors of the process industry: chemical, cement, ceramics, minerals, steel, non-ferrous, industrial water and process engineering. The sectors united under SPIRE include more than 450k individual enterprises, provide jobs for 6.8 million employees and generate annually more than €1.6 billion turnover. SPIRE supports the development of novel technologies for improved resources and energy efficiency in the process industry, making it more sustainable and competitive.

Another example of the PPP is **Energy-efficiency Buildings (EeB)**, which is a partnership between the European Commission and the private sector

⁴⁷ <https://circularitycapital.com>

⁴⁸ <https://www.fundingcircle.com/uk/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.kickstarter.com>

⁵⁰ <https://www.sustainableaccelerator.co.uk/>

⁵¹ <https://fifocapital.com.au/use-sustainability-disrupt-industry/>

represented by the Energy Efficient Buildings Association (E2BA), an Initiative of the European Construction Technology Platform. The multiannual EeB roadmap is the document containing the research and innovation priorities of the private sector, which are essential inputs for the design of the research work programmes by the European Commission. The construction sector is crucial to the EU environment and energy policies as buildings use 40% of total EU energy consumption and generate 36% of GHGs in Europe. Hence, the construction sector is on the critical path to decarbonize the European economy by 2050, which creates a unique opportunity for sustainable business growth provided by the products and related services for both new and refurbished buildings.⁵²

The Joint Technology on Bio-based Industries (BBI) is a €3.7 billion PPP between the EU and Bio-based Industries Consortium. It aims to increase investment in the development of a sustainable bio-based industry sector in Europe by contributing to a more resource-efficient and low-carbon economy, increasing the competitiveness and economic growth of Europe and contributing to establishing Europe as a key player in research demonstration and deployment of advanced bio-based products.

Factories of the Future (FoF) is another PPP initiative aiming at helping EU manufacturing enterprises, in particular SMEs, to adapt to global competitive pressures by developing the necessary enabling technologies across a broad range of sectors. The objective is to help the European industry to meet increasing global consumer demand for greener, more customized and higher quality products through the necessary transition to a demand-driven industry with less waste and better use of resources.

⁵² http://www.futuring-project.eu/static/deliverables/FUTURING_D3.4.pdf

3. Development and exploitation opportunities identified

During the execution of ECOBULK project, significative progress has been achieved in most of the fields that are part of it. In WP2 an extensive study has been carried out regarding design principles and strategies for enhancing the product circularities like surface cleaning techniques or adequate fastener selection. In terms of material development, the work done in WP3 was very diverse comprising from the development of new composite formulations (based on recycled materials or natural fibre reinforcements) and less contaminant binders to new compression moulding for such composites and airway techniques to improve the bonding of nonwoven fabrics. In WP4, the ECOBULK consortium made use of this previous research on designs and materials to work on the manufacturing process of new products. Besides, in WP5, the focus of the ECOBULK consortium was on the implementation of solutions to ease the evaluation, sorting of the bulky waste and the assessment of the reverse logistics chain leading to interesting conclusions. After that, using the information provided by the different points of the value chain studied in the above tasks, WP6 to WP8 have been devoted to the study of the new products' life cycle, their associated business models and the development of software tools to support circularity and increase product data. Nearly all the findings of the project open new paths suitable for researching, and the synergies between the involved partners made possible the application to new funding opportunities to continue with the research.

Based on the funding opportunities exposed and the synergies between ECOBULK partners and developments, this section exposes the plan for seeking additional funding. The exploitation opportunities identified in D8.2 and are taken as starting points to evaluate further progress in the project's objectives. Other future research paths are also included as suggested by project partners which follow the research and development paths carried out in ECOBULK. These opportunities have been analysed together with the available funding tools and possible partnerships to create a vision of future funding beyond ECOBULK. The results of this analysis are available in Table 5. The identifier of each of the opportunities matches that of D8.2, except for the cases where the development path has not been previously identified as an exploitable result (which is the case of opportunities 21 to 25).

Each continuity proposal has a leader and can count with the participation of more ECOBULK partners. The most suitable funding tool has been identified for each opportunity, according to the type of technology to be studied and the consortiums planned. Most partnerships are a subset of the ECOBULK consortium from the same sector (automotive, furniture or construction) or in the same stage of the circular supply chain (design for circularity, material supply, material recovery, etc.). Most ECOBULK large

industrial partners are interested in progressing their way towards developing more circular products, while SMEs and research centres are willing to continue exploring and applying the circular economy concepts and technologies studied. Regarding the funding tool, Horizon Europe is the preferred one due to its focus on sustainability objectives and industrial competitiveness. Some members of the consortium have already started the process of obtaining funds. Up to date, 8 project proposals have been submitted, 3 of which have been accepted, 2 rejected and 3 remain under evaluation.

Table 5 Identified paths that require further funding beyond ECOBULK project.

Lead ECOBULK partner	Partner's country	Identifier	Brief description	TRL at project end	Best fit funding tool	Other ECOBULK partners involved	Remark
TUDELFT	Netherlands	1	Optimal Circular design strategies that provide incentives to the complete value chain	7	Horizon Europe Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Knowledge institutes and companies working on fibre-reinforced plastic (CRF, MICROCAB)	Application for a new Horizon-Europe project on thermosetting fibre reinforced composites done together with CRF. A proposal has also been submitted to NWO on thermoplastic bio-based reinforced composites for wind turbine blades
TECNARO	Germany	3	Pellets from recycled materials suitable for composite moulding fulfilling all required standards in automotive, furniture and construction products	7	Horizon Europe, LIFE programme, Resource Efficient Circular Economy - Innovative Product Cycles initiative, Framework Programme for Research for	MORETTI, CRF, CNR, MAIER, AIMPLAS, BELLVER, FCBA, OH	N/A

Lead partner	ECOBULK Partner's country	Identifier	Brief description	TRL at project end	Best fit funding tool	Other ECOBULK partners involved	Remark
					Sustainable Development		
CONENOR	Finland	4	Circular thermoplastic material formulations and process techniques utilising GFRP-waste as reinforcement	7	Horizon Europe e.g. HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01-02 EU Innovation Fund European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT)	CNR, AIMPLAS, MAIER, CRF	This path can be developed in other interested countries such as: UK, Denmark, Norway, Spain and Germany Other partners involved could be: waste owners, shredding companies, recycled plastics compounders and extrusion companies HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01-02 proposal in collaboration with WindEurope and European Boating Industries being

Lead partner	ECOBULK Partner's country	Identifier	Brief description	TRL at project end	Best fit funding tool	Other ECOBULK partners involved	Remark
							studied.
IRIS	Spain	5	Use of plasma technology in materials as pre-treatment to improve the properties and durability of materials	5	Horizon Europe CL5-2022-D2-01-04: Towards creating an integrated manufacturing value chain in Europe.	N/A	Technology applied to new sectors due to the lack of interest in the consortium.
NTT	Italy	6	Non-toxic and non-pollution plastic and fibre DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) solvent cleaning	7	Horizon Europe, National Operational Programme (NOP), National and regional funding and policy measures	N/A	N/A
COVENTIVE	United Kingdom	7	Flax and Carbon Fibre (CF) long fibre reinforced thermoplastics (LFT) pellets using recycled fibres for the automotive sector	7	H2020 FTI funding - it is well designed for technologies making the transition into commercial production	N/A	Application for EU FTI funding not successful. Eurostars funding gained, focused on upscaling the output volume of all fibre and

Lead partner	ECOBULK	Partner's country	Identifier	Brief description	TRL at project end	Best fit funding tool	Other ECOBULK partners involved	Remark
								polymer varieties.
MAIER		Spain	8.1	Automotive parts for aesthetic applications made of recycled thermoplastic reinforces compounds by injection moulding processes	7	To be defined	N/A	N/A
CONENOR		Finland	9	GFRP-waste reinforced moisture-resistant composite panels and profiles for outdoor structures, animal shelters and concrete casting etc.	7	Private. Direct with extrusion companies, wooden product component manufacturers and end-market appliance suppliers	N/A	Interested countries: Denmark, Norway, UK
KEAS		Turkey	10	New bio-based binders or advanced binders enhancing particleboard production with increasing % of waste particleboard	7	H2020, ERA-NET	AIMPLAS	Proposals presented and rejected to H2020/BBI-JU and ERA-NET: Forest Value.

Lead partner	ECOBULK Partner's country	Identifier	Brief description	TRL at project end	Best fit funding tool	Other ECOBULK partners involved	Remark
TECHNOPLANTS	Italy	11	Optimising the airway and thermos/bonding system for nonwoven composite using natural and regenerated fibres according to the final outcome	7	Horizon Europe, COSME, Public contracts, National and regional funding and policy measures, National Operational Programme (NOP)	NTT, MORETTI	N/A
TOMRA	Germany	13	Recover the desired purity of desired materials out of bulky EoL waste streams for further reprocessing; evaluate the composition of different bulky waste streams and automotive waste streams	7	Horizon Europe, Resource Efficient Circular Economy - Innovative Product Cycles initiative, German Resource Efficiency Programme (ProgRes II)	BELLVER, ITENE, AIMPLAS, COVENTIVE, CNR, NTT, TUDELFT, ISWA, LIPOR	
UPC	Spain	14	Decision-making systems through platform, tool, data for complaints process	6	Horizon Europe, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs)	IRIS, ANSYS, ITENE	

Lead partner	ECOBULK	Partner's country	Identifier	Brief description	TRL at project end	Best fit funding tool	Other ECOBULK partners involved	Remark
IRIS		Spain	15	Quality assurance system to support end-users to guarantee quality compliance of materials and product manufacture in all circular economy processes.	7	Horizon Europe CL5-2022-D2-01-04: Towards creating an integrated manufacturing value chain in Europe.	UPC	Possibility to further extended and validated in other sectors merged with UPC developed technology
UPC		Spain	16	Platform for connecting the users and stakeholders	6	Horizon Europe, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH)	IRIS, ANSYS, ITENE	
CONENOR		Finland	21	New weather-resistant composite railroad crosstie utilising GFRP waste mixed recycled polyethylene PE and/or PP	6	Horizon 2020 Call: H2020-SC5-2018-2019-2020	N/A	Project proposal launched. "CIRCUSE" SEP-210648148
CRANFIELD		UK	22	New bio-based adhesive formulation of gluten and sodium alginate. Further development by incorporating with current synthetic wood adhesives in the market to reach possible exfoliate outcomes.	7	Waste Resource Action Program Other suited funding tools: Zero Waste Scotland, Innovative UK, Knowledge Transfer Network, UK research and	N/A	

Lead partner	ECOBULK Partner's country	Identifier	Brief description	TRL at project end	Best fit funding tool	Other ECOBULK partners involved	Remark
					innovation		
TECNARO	Germany	23	Biocompounds based on the addition of a natural antioxidant, a natural flame retardant that is effective in maintaining properties during reprocessing and after the recycling process, fulfilling all required standards in automotive, furniture and construction products	5 to 7	Horizon Europe, LIFE programme, Resource Efficient Circular Economy - Innovative Product Cycles initiative, Framework Programme for Research for Sustainable Development	MORETTI, CRF, CNR, MAIER, AIMPLAS, BELLVER, FCBA, OH	
KEAS	Turkey	24	Development Formaldehyde-Free Resin Systems by obtaining tanning from red pine tree bark, which is the industrial waste of the company, and production of wood-based composite panels with the resin.	7	National funding source	N/A	Funding obtained from national programme. TÜBİTAK TEYDEB 1501. Other partners: Bursa technical university and Istanbul technical university

Lead partner	ECOBULK	Partner's country	Identifier	Brief description	TRL at project end	Best fit funding tool	Other ECOBULK partners involved	Remark
KEAS		Turkey	25	Bio-adhesive development with nanocellulose extracted through microwave technology	6	International partnership	N/A	Proposal presented and accepted for funding at the programme Newton – Katip Çelebi Fund (transforming systems through partnership). Other partners: Nottingham University and Koç University

4. Conclusions

This report constitutes the last version of D1.4. The first approach for seeking additional funding was presented in M24 according to the ECOBULK opportunities at the date.

The current version of the deliverable provides the funding landscape supporting the CE initiatives and the identified development and exploitation opportunities. An overview of the main funding instruments (public and private) at the European, national and regional levels available to different types of organisations seeking investment in the CE is presented. These funding instruments are contrasted with the opportunities created from the ECOBULK project, identifying the most suitable ones for continuously progressing on ECOBULK objectives. From this analysis, the European framework and particularly Horizon Europe is the most promising funding instrument due to its sustainability focus and the clusters concept to improve industrial competitiveness. The consortiums that will be created after the project end will be smaller partnerships within the same sector (furniture, construction or automotive) or chain stage (design, circular material supply, recovery, etc.). Most ECOBULK large industrial partners are interested in progressing their way towards developing more circular products, while SMEs and research centres are willing to continue exploring and applying the circular economy concepts and technologies studied.

This deliverable should be considered as a tool for providing key information available to all of those interested in the EU funding programmes, as well as other national and regional programmes (both public and private) supporting the circular economy initiatives.

Appendix A European financial instruments for research and innovation in CE until 2020

A.1 Horizon 2020

The Horizon 2020 Work Programme supports the objectives of the CE and industrial competitiveness in the EU in a wide range of industrial and service activities, including process industries, manufacturing, and new business models. It also explores a pilot approach to help innovators facing regulatory obstacles (e.g. ambiguous legal provisions), by setting up agreements with stakeholders and public authorities ('innovation deals').⁵³

This initiative adds to a wide range of existing Horizon 2020 programmes supporting innovative projects relevant to the CE, in fields such as waste prevention and management, food waste, remanufacturing, sustainable process industry, industrial symbiosis, and the bioeconomy. The current main Horizon 2020 work programme, as well as all thematic sections and the general annexes describing general rules such as standard admissibility conditions and eligibility criteria, types of action, selection and award criteria, can be found at <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/>. Each thematic section is self-contained and describes the overall objectives, the respective calls for proposals, and the topics within each call.

In the Working Programme 2018–20, €941 million is allocated in the form of grants to the CE initiatives under the headline of 'Connecting economic and environmental gains – the Circular Economy'.⁵⁴ The programme is open to everyone and the rules and procedures to follow are simple enough to allow participants to focus on what is important: research, innovation and results. The SME Instrument of the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation offers funding and support particularly for SMEs' innovative projects to help them grow and expand their activities into other countries.

A summary of actions available through the H2020 programme is provided in Table 6.

⁵³ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2015/EN/1-2015-614-EN-F1-1.PDF>

⁵⁴ Stuchtey et al., 2018. The Role of Business in the Circular Economy Markets, Processes and Enabling Policies. Report of e CEPS Task Force, available at: <https://www.ceps.eu/publications/role-business-circular-economy-markets-processes-and-enabling-policies>

Table 6 Summary of actions available through Horizon 2020 programme (source: <http://www.futuring-project.eu>)

Type of action	Minimum participations	Funding Rate	Typical Duration	Average EC Contribution	Goal
Research & Innovation Action – RIA	≥ 3 legal entities from 3 MS/AC	100%	36-48 months	€2.0 – 5.0M	Collaborative research projects
Innovation Action – IA	≥ 3 legal entities from 3 MS/AC	70% or 100% for non-profit organisation	30-36 months	€2.0 – 5.0M	Produce plans & arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services
Coordination & Support Action – CSA	1 legal entity	100%	12-30 months	€0.5 – 2.0M	Accompanying measures (standardisation, dissemination, policy dialogues etc.); Does not include research
SME Instrument	1 SME from MS/AC	3 phases: Phase 1: lump sum of € 50K / project Phase 2: € 1 – 2.5M / project (1-2 years) (70% of eligible costs reimbursed) Phase 3 : minor funding (other support)			Combination of demonstration activities (testing, prototyping, ...), market replication
Fast Track to Innovation – FTI	≤ 5 legal entities from 5 MS/AC	70% or 100% for non-profit organisation		≤ €3.0M	Produce plans & arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services
ERA-NET	≥ 2 legal entities from MS/AC	33% Maximum EU contribution, complemented by national funds		≤ €10M	Co-funding of regional, national & international doctoral & fellowship programmes

The H2020 funding programme will soon come to an end and Horizon Europe, a program with €100 billion for research and innovation, will succeed it from 2021 until 2027.

A.2 COSME

The programme for the Competitiveness of Enterprises and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (COSME) was created to improve access to finance for SMEs through two major financial instruments:⁵⁵

- **Loan Guarantee Facility (LGF)** - provides guarantees and counter-guarantees for financial intermediaries (e.g. guarantee organisations, banks, leasing companies) to help them provide more loan and lease finance to SMEs. This facility will also include the securitisation of SME debt finance portfolios.
- **Equity Facility for Growth (EFG)** - dedicated to investments in risk capital funds that provide venture capital and mezzanine finance to expansion and growth-stage SMEs, in particular those operating across borders.

COSME has a budget of over €1.3 billion to fund these financial instruments that facilitate access to loans and equity finance for SMEs where market gaps have been identified. Thanks to this budget, it is foreseen to mobilise up to €25 billion in financing from financial intermediaries via leverage effects. The financial instruments are managed by the European Investment Fund (EIF) in cooperation with financial intermediaries in EU countries. COSME financial instruments are designed mostly for SMEs or entrepreneurs looking for debt or equity finance.

A.3 InnovFin

InnovFin (EU Finance for Innovators) is a joint initiative launched by the European Investment Bank Group in cooperation with the European Commission under Horizon 2020. InnovFin aims to facilitate and accelerate access to finance for innovative businesses and other innovative entities in Europe.⁵⁶

InnovFin provides €24 billion in financial instruments for innovative SMEs, startups and midcaps, made available through Horizon 2020 and the EIB Group. Its financing tools cover a wide range of loans, guarantees and equity-type funding, which can be tailored to innovators' needs. Financing is either provided directly or via a financial intermediary, most usually a bank or a fund. InnovFin is available to companies and other entities of all sizes and ages and across all eligible sectors in the EU Member States and Associated Countries.

A.4 The European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI)

⁵⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/access-to-finance/cosme-financial-instruments_en

⁵⁶ <https://www.eib.org/en/products/blending/innovfin/index.htm>

The Investment Plan for Europe, the so-called Juncker Plan, is one of the European Commission's top priorities. It focuses on boosting investments to create jobs and growth by making smarter use of new and existing financial resources, removing obstacles to investment and providing visibility and technical assistance to investment projects. The EFSI is the central pillar of the Juncker Plan. The projects and agreements approved for financing under the EFSI so far are expected to mobilise more than €236.1 billion in investments and support over 454 000 SMEs across all 28 Member States.

EFSI is a €26 billion guarantee from the EU budget, complemented by a €7.5 billion allocation of the European Investment Banks' capital. With EFSI support, the European Investment Bank Group is providing funding for economically viable projects, especially for projects with a higher risk profile than usually taken on by the Bank. It will focus on sectors of key importance for the European economy, including:⁵⁷

- Strategic infrastructure including digital, transport and energy
- Education, research, development and innovation
- Renewable energy and resource efficiency
- Support for small and mid-sized businesses

EFSI is demand-driven and provides support for projects everywhere in the EU, including cross-border projects. There are no geographic or sector quotas. Projects are considered based on their merits. The CE per se is not targeted but the environment and resource efficiency is defined as an eligible sector and made up 4% (€9.4 billion) of the mobilised investment as of September 2017. Circular business models may also be eligible in transport infrastructure, R&D&I, ICT, and SME/mid-cap support.⁵⁸

A.5 Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance (IPA II)

The Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance (IPA) is the mean by which the EU supports reforms in the 'enlargement countries' with financial and technical help. The IPA funds build up the capacities of the countries throughout the accession process, resulting in progressive, positive developments in the region. For the period 2007-2013 IPA had a budget of €11.5 billion; its successor, IPA II, was built on the results already achieved by dedicating €11.7 billion for the period 2014-2020. Current beneficiaries are Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo*, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, and Turkey.⁵⁹

IPA II can support investments in public administration reform, rule of law, sustainable economy, people and agriculture and rural development. IPA II

⁵⁷ <https://www.eib.org/en/efsi/what-is-efsi/index.htm>

⁵⁸ Stuchtey et al., 2018. The Role of Business in the Circular Economy Markets, Processes and Enabling Policies. Report of the CEPS Task Force, available at: <https://www.ceps.eu/publications/role-business-circular-economy-markets-processes-and-enabling-policies>

⁵⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/instruments/overview_en

support for economic development is diverse and depends on the countries' economic structure. Actions include preparing feasibility studies for loans from the International Financial Institutions, support to SMEs to improve access to finance, setting up quality infrastructure agencies, and boosting the energy and transport infrastructure.